

ASEAN's Flow of Professional Workers: Challenges and Solutions for Cambodia

Sao Chantola ✉

The University of Cambodia, Phnom Penh, Cambodia

Ka Mathul

Royal Academic of Cambodia, Phnom Penh, Cambodia

Ro Vannak

Faculty of Social Sciences, the University of Cambodia, Phnom Penh, Cambodia

Abstract

The challenges and solutions for Cambodia from the free flow of skilled labor in the ASEAN Economic Community has been a heated topic argued among Cambodians, people in charge of skilled workers, learners and professionals, as Cambodia managed himself joining the ASEAN Economic Community at the starting of 2016. In order to understand the challenges and solutions more in detail, a study was conducted; it employed a quantitative approach, and it was conducted with a questionnaire delivered directly to 396 students who were pursuing their studies from associate's degrees to Doctoral degrees at five different universities in Phnom Penh, Cambodia. As the results, a descriptive statistical analysis in the Statistical Package for the Social Science, version 23.0, showed that there were challenges for Cambodia, indicated by 75 per cent of respondents thought that the country lacked skilled workers to challenge the ASEAN's professionals. 70 per cent of participants considered the inflow of foreign skilled labor as a threat to local jobs seekers, while 81 per cent of respondents supported the statement "the imbalanced agreement implementation on skilled labor in ASEAN is another barrier in ASEAN's jobs finding for Cambodian skilled workers". Toward the solutions to reduce the challenges and to better the chances for Cambodians, significant suggestions have been shared; firstly, education reform, further vocations and trainings for Cambodians should be better improved. Secondly, creating more local jobs should be further done and thirdly, Cambodian skilled workers should improve their knowledge of the English language, as it is very important in Cambodia, ASEAN and the world in pursuing their present and future's studies and works.

Keywords: *Flow, professional, workers, challenges, solutions.*

JEL Classification codes: *F66, J01, J21.*

Suggested citation: Chantola, S., Mathul, K., & Vannak, R. (2025). ASEAN's Flow of Professional Workers: Challenges and Solutions for Cambodia. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(2), 72-83. DOI: 10.59324/ejmeb.2025.2(2).09

Introduction

The Association of Southeast Asian Nations was established on 08 August 1967. By 1999, the Association had reached its size of ten Member States, encompassing Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Indonesia, Lao, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam, and the ASEAN Economic Community was being fashioned in 2016 to represent 625 million people and become the world's seventh largest economy; one of the core principles of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations Economic Community was a free flow of skilled labor (Johnson, 2015) that all ten members of ASEAN had signed on for. The free flow of skilled worker focused on eight selected fields, namely engineering, architecture, accounting, nursing, medical practitioners, dentists, tourism practitioners, and land surveyors. Those professionals could seek jobs within the region of ASEAN. As a member of ASEAN, Cambodian professionals of the above eight are able to find works in any countries in this ASEAN region.

There has recently been a lot of discussion in relation to the challenges and solutions for Cambodia from the free mobility of skilled labor in the ASEAN. This has led to questioning by the Cambodian as "What are the challenges and solutions for Cambodian professionals in the free movements of skilled labor in the ASEAN Economic Community?"

This dissertation is raising the topic about the free flow of skilled labor forces in the ASEAN to be studied in order to identify the challenges that Cambodian professionals may face, and what should be the solutions for Cambodia to make itself stronger and more competitive with more powerful resources, and this would help the country improve.

Methodology

Research Design and Instruments

This study employs a quantitative method that is manipulated to get universities students' perceptions on the challenges and solutions for Cambodia from the free flow of skilled labor in the ASEAN economic community. In this case, quantitative research method is found best matched with this study for it measures various views and opinions of a large number of the chosen respondents. The survey questionnaires were subjected to 396 university students in Phnom Penh to explore participants' views.

Data Analysis Methods

The study is conducted with a set of questionnaires that are delivered directly to 396 students who are pursuing their studies from associate to doctoral degree at five different universities in Phnom Penh as the live-evidences. The survey asked universities students the concerns and recommendations on the free flow of skilled labor migration of Cambodia into the ASEAN and data collected are analyzed by frequency descriptive analysis in the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS), version 23.0.

Selection of Research Participants

The scope and limitation of this study is on the sample size of 396 participants at five Cambodian universities in Phnom Penh where it is the core educational institutions of Cambodia. Participants in this study were entirely voluntary and anonymous and all of them were well informed in advance about the purposes of the study before they decided to participate in the survey. Students at universities are aimed for this study for several reasons; first, mostly, after graduating, universities' students become skilled workers and they are intellectuals who are considered as the potential participants and much related with future skilled labor. Second, the study is also focusing on young potential skilled workers, while others like the present's skilled workers are a mixture of ages;

further, students are also found as the main migrants in the region as it is written that “ASEAN’s growing student migrant population is a potential source of high-skilled labor that could increase competitiveness in the future,” (Testaverde, Moroz, Hollweg, & Schmillen, 2018).

Sample Size Calculation

When searching for a popular formula to determine the research sample size, the great statistician, Taro Yamane’s formula would be the best choice (Yamane, 2016); therefore, Taro Yamane sample size calculation method is employed for determining the sample size of this study.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N \times e^2} \quad (1)$$

(n: sample size, N: population size, and e is acceptable error (e: 0.05)

e^2 : 0.0025 (Yamane, 2016)

Total numbers of students studying at 5 universities is 42103

To get Sample Size, the researcher divided total population by 1 plus a total population and time with the square of acceptable error.

$$n = \frac{N=42103}{1 + 42103 \times (e: 0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{42103}{1 + 105.2575} = \frac{42103}{106.2575} = 396.23 = 396$$

Research’s Pilot

To improve the study’s reliability, research questionnaires have been checked by advisors, experienced researchers and professors and after receiving feedback, questionnaires have been piloted on a group of students at the University of Cambodia to check whether that they could be easily understood to avoid possible misinterpretations. After they had been re-edited and finalized with comments received from the pilot study, 396 questionnaires were administered to university students who are taking their undergraduate and graduate studies at five universities in Phnom Penh. 395 questionnaires have been returned, a good 99.75% response rate. The data information from the questionnaires received was then analyzed by frequency descriptive analysis in Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), Version 23.0.

Participants’ Profile (Sample size, n = 396)

395 university students replied to the questionnaires, a nearly one hundred (100) percent response rate (99.75%). The profile of the participants in this study can be seen in the following Table.

Table 1. Frequency and Percent of Demographic Data

Background	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	173	44
Female	215	54
Other	3	1
No response	4	1
Age		
18-20	117	30
21-25	235	59
26-30	23	6

31-35	8	2
36 above	8	2
No response	4	1
Education		
Associate	16	4
Bachelor	323	82
Master	38	10
PhD	12	3
Other	4	1
No response	2	0.5
Year of Study		
Year 1	69	17
Year 2	72	18
Year 3	96	24
Year 4	109	28
Other	48	12

Results

Figure 1. Skilled Workers Shortages to Challenge the ASEAN's Professionals

“Cambodia still lacked skilled workers to challenge the ASEAN’s skilled workers”. Replying to this belief on Cambodian skills shortages, 33 per cent and 42 per cent of participants strongly agreed and agreed respectively, with 15 per cent have no responses, with 7 per cent and 3 per cent disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 2. Inflow of Foreign Skilled Labor, a Threat to Local Job Seekers

“Inflow of foreign skilled professionals is a threat to Cambodian local jobs seekers”.

Responding to this concerning opinion, 29 per cent and 41 per cent strongly agreed and agreed respectively, with 15 per cent said that they have no comment about this, while 13 per cent disagreed and 2 per cent strongly disagreed (Figure 2).

Figure 3. Imbalanced Practice on Skilled Labor (local first, ASEAN second), the Barrier in Jobs Finding in ASEAN

The third finding is that 14 per cent and 67 per cent of participants strongly agreed and agreed respectively with the statement “the imbalanced agreement practice on skilled labor, local first, ASEAN second, the barrier in ASEAN’s jobs finding” with 12 per cent of them choose neutral, having no idea, while other 5 per cent and 2 per cent disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively with this statement (Figure 3).

Solutions for Cambodia’s Skilled Labors

To reduce the challenges and to better the opportunities for Cambodian skilled workers, recommendations have been shared by respondents; firstly, education reform, further vocations and trainings for Cambodians should be better developed. Secondly, creating more jobs, it includes attracting more local and foreign investors to Cambodia should be further done and thirdly, Cambodian skilled workers should have higher knowledge of English language as it is very important in Cambodia, the ASEAN and the world in pursuing present and future studies and works.

Discussion

Skilled Labor Shortages to Challenge the ASEAN’s

Replying to the concerning opinion that claimed “Cambodia lacks skilled workers to challenge the ASEAN’s professionals”, 33 per cent and 42 per cent of 395 universities’ students strongly agreed and agreed, respectively. This outcome is also found supported by the experts’ opinions as there are extractions “Cambodia was lacking highly educated people; most professionals and the well-trained skilled laborers were found disqualified to compete with other skilled laborers in ASEAN. Cambodia may stand behind other countries in the region in terms of skills. Many are not being able to compete with other countries like Singapore and Malaysia in a single jobs market,” (Dai, 2015). Chantol (2015) stated that there were a number of difficulties that Cambodia has been facing; one of them was the shortages of skilled workforces. Chheang Vannarith, a lecturer at the

University of Leeds, told the Voice of America in Khmer in a Television studio interview that Cambodia would be challenging at a regional level. ASEAN states were working to have economic integration since 2015, but observers have claimed that Cambodia faced problem of human resources shortages in order to compete in the integrated economic community (Mony, 2013), and according to part of research which was conducted to ask CEOs to assess the ease of finding skilled employees, business leaders in Cambodia reported the talent shortages (Zahidi, 2016). Cambodia has a deficit of skilled professionals, and its economies are suffering from a lack of technical education, which was necessary for industrial development (Gnanasagaran, 2018), and Cambodia Vocational Education Specialist, Lim Solinn told Khmer Times that companies operating in Cambodia were facing challenges due to skills gaps (Mathew, 2022). Similarly, Minister of Labor and Vocational Training, Ith Samheng, stated that “Our country, we have a lot of labor in terms of labor force, but we still lack high-skilled labor to fulfill the needs of employers,” (Carruthers, 2023). According to Chheang Vannarith, ASEAN necessitates a sufficient number of skilled laborers with skills of such as engineering, accounting, medical, land surveying, and English proficiency (Vannarith, 2017).

Inflow of Foreign Skilled Professionals, a Threat to Local Jobs Seekers

Responding to the worrying idea “Inflow of foreign skilled professionals is a threat to local Job seekers”, 29 per cent and 41 per cent of universities students strongly agreed and agreed, respectively, and this was backed up by statement “Some Cambodians have thought that they would not be able to challenge with skilled workers from other countries and that nearly all the jobs can be lost”, “Cambodia has a skills shortage that the country has to continue to accept workers from other countries,” said Chan Sophal, Director for the Centre for Policy Studies said (Phnom Penh Post, 2015).

Cambodia with his low to medium-skill workers could see a flowing in of better educated skilled workers. D’Amico, managing director of human resource broker HRINC said “it would surely increase the competition for these jobs and Cambodians may not benefit from these opportunities,” (Chandara, 2015; Phnom Penh Post, 2015). The free mobility of labor leads serious challenges for Cambodian labor forces as they will have to challenge for jobs with foreign skilled worker; some Cambodian students have already expressed their concern of not having the ability to compete for jobs after they graduated schools (Vichet & Sokha, 2015). Kang Chandararoth, head of the Economics Unit at the Independent Analysis Group said that “Less Cambodian students have technical knowledge and this field of jobs would probably be influenced by foreign skilled workers.”; showing similar vision, Chan Sophal, Director for the Centre for Policy Studies, said “Cambodians have a belief that they would not be able to compete with workers from other countries and that the jobs would be taken,” he explained that Cambodia has a skills shortage (Phnom Penh Post, 2015). “Our skills are limited and if we cannot find local staff, we have to find them from abroad; if we continue to allow international experts to catch up on our work, our human resources will slowly develop,” said Ang Kim Eang, CEO of Grand Angkor Tours (Phnom Penh Post, 2016). Seang Vathana Tann, an accounting student at Cam-Ed Business School said that the competition for local high-skill jobs will get tougher. “Foreign workers will come to occupy the top jobs and it will be hard for the local skilled professionals to compete with them,” she said (Chandara, 2015). Some people are concerned that the education system and the quality of Cambodian graduates, on average are below some other countries within the region. The competition through the free flow of skilled professionals within the region was seen by some Cambodian students as a threat on their future to get employment (Sokha & Vichet , 2015).

Local First, ASEAN Second, the Barrier in ASEAN’s Job Finding

14 percent and 67 percent of participants strongly agreed and agreed respectively with the statement “Local first, ASEAN second, the barrier in ASEAN’s job finding for Cambodians”, and is it seen

assisted by statements as there are some biased regulations and practices that lead to some difficulties in skills mobility, such as the condition that jobs are firstly reserved for their own citizens; the inequalities of recognition of foreign skilled education, training and experience (Siphana, 2015). Individual country faces restrictions on certain jobs prepared for their own citizens and despite the Mutual Recognition Arrangement within the AEC for greater regional skilled free mobility for practitioners in professions (Yap, 2016). Economist, Professor at School of Public Policy, Yeoh Lam Keong, told The Online Citizen, he cautioned that “we do need to be more careful in terms of free flow of labor even skilled labor.” This hollows out domestic skills long term and keeps us dependent on foreign professionals. “It also prevents firms from higher value skilled occupations and going for cheap professionals with lower human capital content.” (Loh, 2016). As actions and implementation on free flow of skilled labor in the region of ASEAN are in the lengthy and complicated processes, this unsmooth implementation of ASEAN’s MRA will probably affect negatively on Cambodian skilled workers to the region for there are still biases on them who plan to find jobs in the ASEAN. Migrant-sending countries are gearing up to be more proactive, while labor-receiving countries are more careful about professional mobility. Immigration policies for foreign workers in some countries are also seen to be more restrictive. Migration procedures across Association of Southeast Asian Nations stay restrictive. Costly and time-consuming recruitment processes that limit the number of foreign migrants allowed in the country, as well as rigid labor rules, limit workers' employment options and negatively impact their well-being (World Bank, 2017). MRA is widely regarded as the most important tool for professional mobility in ASEAN; yet, recognition remains a complicated and time-consuming procedure across ASEAN countries, and MRA implementation is plagued with challenges (Siphana, 2015; SMU, 2016), and the free flow of skilled labor in ASEAN was not fully operational, and the ASEAN lacked specific plans to maintain this flow of experts (Vannarith, 2017); even mutual recognition agreements negotiated by countries to ease cross-border movement of professionals, according to Rastam Mohd Isa, president and CEO of the Malaysian Institute for Strategic and International Studies, have been poorly implemented (SMU, 2015); in an interview, Jayant Menon, a senior economist at the Asian Development Bank, indicated that preparations for skilled labor mobility in the region will need to continue for another ten years before the AEC can be fully realized (Parikh, 2015). Mutual recognition agreements, which allow trained professionals to freely relocate within the ASEAN Economic Community, are not yet fully operational (Johanna, 2018). It suggested that country like Thailand should work to make workers entry procedures less expensive, Singapore is being motivated to go on to improve protections for migrant workers and to build public belief that the migration system is taking care the welfare of workers, and Malaysia is advised that it should collaborate more closely with both employers and skilled labors sending nations(Niles, 2018).

Solutions for Cambodia

Among the outcomes received from research’s survey, 116 respondents shared further recommendations in order to narrow down the challenges and to strengthen the opportunities for Cambodian skilled labors.

Firstly, 72 of research participants suggested the significances of strengthening education, vocational training for Cambodian skilled workers that these opinions are really observed paralleled with the suggestions and recommendations expressed by key persons in charge of skilled professionals in Cambodia as the opinions have been extracted

“Education improvement is needed for creating the right skills for the work market. Education reform is very important so students are equipped with the desired skills to satisfy employers' wishes”, “Education and higher-level skills are crucial for this country,” (ILO, ADB, 2015). Similarly, Dai (2015) claimed that developing education system is found as the vital step, and

strengthening the local skills ought to be done in order to possess enough the country's professionals. Further, Heng Sour, director general for administration and finance at the Ministry of Labour and Vocational Training said "Cambodia needs to put a stronger emphasis on education and vocational training," (Runcie, 2016). "Participating in skills development, the training centers should be built to certify professionals that meet ASEAN Economic Community's standards, allowing them to work within the region," stated Try Chhiv, deputy director-general of the Ministry of Tourism (Phnom Penh Post, 2016). According to CVEA (2017), sentences are seen written that "As inter-ASEAN competition between its members in terms of labor flows, Cambodia must strengthen the capacity of its own human resources in order to meet the competitive labor market of ASEAN in the coming years and to ensure employment opportunities inside and outside Cambodia", Chan Sophal, Director of the Centre for Policy Studies in Cambodia said, and he also continued that "The number one priority is to better train and educate our students; this is the only way we can compete." (CVEA, 2017); to develop human resources, the Ministry of Education has seen created vital development by making a lot of skillful labor through vocational courses (Todd, 2015) and the Royal Government of Cambodia of the Fifth Legislature concentrates on the priorities like training of skilled and productive labor to satisfy market demand; develops educational and vocational institutions; encourages private sector participation; and strengthens the standard of education and promote research, technology development and innovation (ILO, 2019).

Secondly, 23 of university students shared comments on providing more local jobs and attracting more investors to Cambodia in order to create more works in the country.

Literature reviews were seen matched with these recommendations, as according to Hai Bun Leng, deputy director of National Employment Agency, the National Career and Productivity Fair in 2017 in Phnom Penh offered about twenty thousand jobs from large companies and organization include bank, micro finance, construction, hotels, and vocational centres, garment industries, and other private agencies (Sokha, 2018). And in terms of foreign investments attraction for creating new jobs, a newly release studied by the Asian Development Bank found that Special Economic Zones (SEZs) in Cambodia have attracted significant levels of foreign investment into Cambodia. The investments have created around 68,000 jobs (CDC, 2015). Foreign direct investment is the key driving force of Cambodia's economic development; China, Japan, South Korea and ASEAN countries are the main sources of the foreign direct investment (FDI) inflow to Cambodia (Vannarith, 2017) and in order to continue its healthy record of growth and build jobs for the country's youth, Cambodia has to attract and encourage new investment, both domestic and foreign. Hing Thoraxy, an economics lecturer at the Royal Academy of Cambodia, said "More investments provide jobs to Cambodian people and provide many benefits to the economy," he said. The government in 2015 released a 10-year industrial development policy (IDP), and the aim of the policy is to attract more Foreign Direct Investment (Kimsay, 2018). In addition, related to new recruitments for government employees, Ministry of Civil Service also prepared to recruit candidates who are qualified enough to work to fill the vacant positions to meet the real need at national and sub-national institutions, municipal and provincial technical departments. The framework provisions for all ministries and institutions for year 2019 include 5,996 civil servants; 18,292 contract officers. Ministry of Civil Service undersecretary of state, Chut Monny said that the government has annually recruited distinguished officers (Dara, 2019).

Thirdly, Cambodian university students expressed their ideas on the significances of English language for skilled worker in both, Cambodia and the ASEAN in pursuing present and future works. 21 of respondents added their comments on the necessary of English language and this suggestion is really seen strongly supported by literature review.

Since Kingdom of Cambodia joined the free market within the past decade, the numbers of English schools have increased noticeably. In 1996, the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports included

English language into the school course of study ranging from Grade 7. George Taylor who worked involved with the project of Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports' project to train English language lecturers, says the rise within the numbers of learner keen to require English lessons has shocked him; he noted in 1996 the number of students studying English has increased by half in only five years. Taylor has observed the increase of English schools in both Phnom Penh and the provinces (Nara, 2001). "English is the official language for ASEAN association that we have to master English because all the speeches have to be translated into English and all conferences are conducted in English", "Knowledge of English is important for promotion and better career opportunities. English has become popular within ASEAN because it is the priority language in ASEAN," said Dr. Hang Chuon Naron, Minister of Education Youth and Sport of Cambodia. He also continued that "It is the opportunity for Cambodian professionals to go out and work in other ASEAN countries, provided we have good English language skills we can work with other members of ASEAN, because English is used as the language of communication in ASEAN," (ACE magazine, 2014). English language is thought as needed and this language will become the common language of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations Economic Community and it must be improved in Cambodia (Todd, 2015). English language is considered as foundation for regional and global competence and it has also been getting more focus from schools and students. At the 14th Annual Cam-TESOL Conference in Phnom Penh, Educational Minister, Hang Chuon Naron stated the values of studying English to easily communicate with people. "Using English is a great way to improve knowledge. It is not just about making friends with foreign friends, but it is the youth's ticket to the future. They need the skills in English to be more competitive and to contribute more to the community," said the Minister (Kumneth, 2018).

Conclusion

By the end of 2015, the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) established a single market and production base in the region. With an ASEAN overall workforce of more than three hundred million people, the AEC will have strong implications in terms of workers migration and the AEC will demand for skilled labor across all countries in the region.

Before and while the free flow of skilled professionals in the ASEAN Economic Community is being taken into the real practices, the challenges and solutions for Cambodia have been raised and debated among general Cambodians, employees, jobs hunters and students. Further, this issue is often heard and seen argued in the seminars, radios, newspapers, written documents and it is observed that there are different ideas towards the challenges and solutions for Cambodia.

To understand the challenges and solutions for Cambodia from the free flow of skilled labor in the ASEAN Economic Community is considered significant and it should be investigated; therefore, this study is of importance in providing information on the challenges and solutions for Cambodia from the free movements of skilled labor in the region of ASEAN.

Regarding quantitative approach, this method is manipulated to get universities students' perceptions on the challenges and solutions for Cambodia in the Free Flow of Skilled Labor in the ASEAN Economic Community and the data from the questionnaires received are analyzed by descriptive frequency analysis in SPSS (version 23). The survey questionnaires are subjected to 396 universities' students in Phnom Penh to explore their views.

Based on the main findings, Cambodian faced the challenges that are observed as the country lacked qualified skilled workers to compete with other ASEAN's skilled professionals and the inflows of foreign skilled labors is seen as a threat to local jobs seekers. Besides, the imbalanced agreement implementation of skilled labor that is still seen in some countries under the condition

“prepares jobs firstly for local and secondly for the ASEAN” is worriedly observed as another barrier in jobs findings in the region for Cambodian skilled workers as well.

The study’s results of the study reveal a waking message for Cambodia to strengthen and further reform its education system in order to produce more qualified and needed skilled professionals in order to have ability to work and challenge for local and international labors markets. Regarding the concerns over the jobs opportunities that is worriedly taken by foreign workers, the government is seen advised to plays more active roles in controlling properly the laws on inflow of foreign workers and creating, reserving job opportunities for local people. Moreover, the agreement on free flow of skilled labor in ASEAN, which was signed by all members should be in double-checked in order to make this agreement accepted and practiced fairly and equally by all countries and this may help Cambodian professionals to find jobs in the whole region rightly and fairly.

To solve the difficulties and to better the opportunities for Cambodian skilled workers, education reform and development for Cambodians should be improved; creating more jobs that includes attracting local and foreign investors to Cambodia should be further done, and skilled workers should have higher knowledge of English as it is very important in Cambodia, the ASEAN and the world in pursuing present and future studies and work.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to express gratitude to reviewers and the editorial team of EJMEB for supporting this article. Their contributions are considered invaluable help for researchers and society. The first author also would like to thank the University of Cambodia for providing the greatest opportunities for him to be successful in the academic life of education to pursue a PhD in International Relations.

Ethical Approval

This article is a part of the author’s PhD dissertation in International Relations at the University of Cambodia, Phnom Penh, Cambodia, and the university has formally approved it.

References

- Asian Development Bank (ADB) & International Labour Organization (ILO). (2015). *Cambodia: Addressing the skills gap*. Retrieved from <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/176283/cambodia-addressing-skills-gap.pdf>
- Council for the Development of Cambodia (CDC). (2015). *Cambodia Industrial Development Policy 2015-2025*. Retrieved from <https://www.cambodiainvestment.gov.kh/content/uploads/2015/09/IDP-English-Version-FINAL1.pdf>
- Carruthers, M. (2023). High-skilled labour key to developing economy. Retrieved from <https://kiripost.com/stories/cambodia-high-skilled-labour-key-to-develop-economy>
- Chandara, S. (2015). Labour market unfazed by AEC. Retrieved from <https://www.phnompenhpost.com/business/labour-market-unfazed-aec>

Chanthol, S. (2015). The preparation of AEC integration: Opportunities and challenges for businesses.

Cambodia Valuers and Estate Agents Association (CVEA). (2017). Cambodian market prospects as the AEC approaches. Retrieved from <https://www.realestate.com.kh/news/cambodian-market-prospects-as-the-aec-approaches>

Dai, C. (2015). How will the ASEAN Economic Community impact Cambodia? Retrieved from <http://chabdai.blogspot.com/2015/08/the-impact-of-asean-economic-community.html>

Dara, V. (2019). Recruitment framework approved. Retrieved from <https://www.phnompenhpost.com/national/recruitment-framework-approved>

Gnanasagarar, A. (2018). Strengthening ASEAN's labour force. Retrieved from <https://theaseanpost.com/article/strengthening-aseans-labour-force>

International Labour Organization (ILO). (2019). *Rectangular Strategy for Growth, Employment, Equity and Efficiency Phase III*. [No URL available]

Johanna, S. (2018). ASEAN's double vision of migration. Retrieved from <http://www.aseannews.net/aseans-double-vision-migration>

Johnson, J. (2015). Will the ASEAN Economic Community mean free movement of labour? Retrieved from <http://www.cipd.asia/people-management-magazine/hr-news-opinion/asean-free-movement-labour>

Kimsay, H. (2018). Inflow of FDI up in first half. Retrieved from <https://www.phnompenhpost.com/business/inflow-fdi-first-half>

Kumrath, S. (2018). Cambodia's English skills soaring upwards. Retrieved from <https://www.khmertimeskh.com/108742/cambodias-english-skills-soaring-upwards>

Loh, A. (2016). The AEC's agreement on free flow of skilled labour needs careful attention. Retrieved from <http://www.theonlinecitizen.com/2016/01/02/the-aecs-agreement-on-free-flow-of-skilled-labour-needs-careful-attention/>

Mathew, M. (2022). Cambodia leads on women's employment in ASEAN region. Retrieved from <https://www.khmertimeskh.com/1169893/cambodia-leads-on-womens-employment-in-asean-region>

Niles, B. (2018). Experts call for ambitious ASEAN migration reforms to drive growth. Retrieved from <https://news.cgtn.com/news>

Phnom Penh Post. (2015). Cheap exports, costly imports: Cambodia's labour dilemma. Retrieved from <https://www.phnompenhpost.com/business/cheap-exports-costly-imports-cambodias-labour-dilemma>

Phnom Penh Post. (2016). Cambodia will be the goods center when integrating with ASEAN. Retrieved from <https://www.phnompenhpost.com/business/cambodia-will-be-goods-center-when-integrating-asean>

Runcie, A. (2016). Cambodia suffering a lack of depth in skilled-worker pool. Retrieved from <https://www.phnompenhpost.com/business/cambodia-suffering-lack-depth-skilled-worker-pool>

Siphana, S. (2015). Free flow of skilled labor in ASEAN: A risk for Cambodian graduates?

Singapore Management University (SMU). (2016). Managing skills challenges in ASEAN-5. Retrieved from <https://socsc.smu.edu.sg>

- Sokha, O. (2018). Cambodia to host National Career and Productivity Fair 2018. Retrieved from <https://information.gov.kh>
- Testaverde, M., Moroz, H., Hollweg, C. H., & Schmillen, A. (2018). *The impacts of migration in ASEAN countries*. Retrieved from <https://elibrary.worldbank.org/doi>
- Todd, W. E. (2015). ASEAN integration: An opportunity for business in Cambodia. Retrieved from <http://www.thecambodiaherald.com/opinion/asean-integration-an-opportunity-for-business-in-cambodia>
- Vannarith, C. (2017). Opportunity and challenges for Cambodia from the ASEAN Economic Community integration. [Interview]. Voice of America (VOA).
- Vichet, S., & Sokha, H. (2015). Free flow of skilled labor in ASEAN: A risk for Cambodian graduates? Retrieved from <http://www.shs-encounters-cambodia>
- World Bank. (2017). *Migrating to opportunity: Overcoming barriers to labour mobility in Southeast Asia*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/region/eap/publication/migrating-to-opportunity-overcoming-barriers-to-labour-mobility-in-southeast-asia>
- Zahidi, S. (2016). The next industrial revolution is coming to Southeast Asia. Retrieved from <http://time.com/4347339/asean-world-economic-forum/>
- Yamane, T. (2016). What is Yamane sample calculation? Retrieved from <https://www.quora.com/What-is-Yamane-sample-calculation>

